

GENDER POLICY IN UZBEKISTAN IS AN IMPORTANT CRITERION FOR GUARANTEEING HUMAN RIGHTS

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Kalit soʻzlar: Gender politics, guarantee, criteria, equality, politics, jurisprudence.

Many do not fully understand the meaning of this concept. Gender sociology characterizes it as the possibility of equal participation of representatives of both sexes in various spheres of personal and public life. Equality in this case should not be seen as an antithesis of gender difference - rather, it is the opposite of gender inequality. Its essence is to prove that both men and women have the same rights to work, receive education, vote, self-realization, etc. Ongoing gender inequality in various aspects of life necessitates a constant struggle against this negative and uncivilized phenomenon. International standards of Gender equality in law, gender equality is enshrined by the United Nations International Organization in the conventions of 1952 and 1967. In 1997, the European Union developed gender equality standards:

- * equal treatment of men and women at work;
- * implementation of safety at work for pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and are breastfeeding;
- * equal pay;
- * the application of punitive measures in relation to leaders who allow discriminatory actions.

In terms of the introduction of Gender equality, positive shifts in education should be noted separately. That is, since 2017, the activities of correspondence departments in various specialties have been restored in most higher educational institutions. This form of Education allows young women to receive higher education without prejudice to child care and the fulfillment of other family obligations.

Taking this opportunity, I consider it appropriate to quote President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech in the Senate of the in June 2019:

"I am much thought out by the stereotype that appears in the minds of our people. Usually we respect a woman primarily as a mother, a guardian of the family stronghold. This is undoubtedly true. But today every woman should be not only an ordinary observer, but also an active and enterprising participant in the democratic transformations taking place in the country."

On this day, at the invitation of the president, for the first time in the history of the country, a woman was elected to the presidency of the Senate – Tanzila Norboeva. It is known that Mrs. Norboeva served as Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan, chairman of the women's committee of Uzbekistan.

Referring to the legislative measures in this area, in order to further improve the legal framework for the provision and protection of women's rights in Uzbekistan, in September 2019, the laws “on guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men” and “on protection of women from harassment and violence” were adopted. Almost all UN agencies, including the UN Development Program, the UN Population Fund (YUNFPA), the UN children's fund (UNICEF), the UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, the UN Office for drugs and crime, the International Organization for Migration, have made their comments and suggestions on these two laws.

In the decree of the Senate of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 28, 2021 No. 297-IV “on approval of the strategy for achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan by 2030” over the past four years, large-scale reforms have been carried out aimed at achieving equal rights and opportunities for women and men, ensuring their equal participation in

The issue of Gender equality has risen to the level of Public Policy, and 25 legislative acts related to the industry have been adopted.

The commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan on issues of Gender equality, the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan established the Committee on issues of women's and gender equality.

For the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the number of women in Parliament reached the level corresponding to the recommendations set by the UN, the number of women in Parliament reached almost 32% and reached the 37th place among 190 parliaments in the world.

The share of women in management positions reached 27 percent, in parties-44 percent, in higher education-40 percent, in entrepreneurship-35 percent.

In order to provide socio-economic support for women and work with them at the address, the "women's notebook" system was introduced and it was established to allocate 300 billion soums annually from the state budget.

Needy girls who have lost their parents or one of them, have no breadwinners a system of reimbursement of tuition fees for single women has been introduced, and the number of grants for girls from needy families in admission to higher education has doubled.

In order to develop women's entrepreneurship, more than 224 thousand women-girls were allocated a preferential loan in the amount of a total of 6.9 trillion soums.

The reforms carried out in the field have a positive effect on the place of our country in the international rankings, and in the index of women, business and law of the World Bank, Uzbekistan in 2020 was ranked among the 27 countries

that carried out significant reforms on women's rights and gender equality and ranked 134th among the 190 countries.

Uzbekistan has always shown its commitment to the goals and principles of the UN Charter and other generally accepted norms of international law.

At the UN General Assembly summit on Sustainable Development in September 2015, resolution 70 adopted 125 target tasks and 206 indicators to achieve 16 national goals that are relevant for our country.

In particular, in conclusion, in the field of sustainable development

The 5th goal is to ensure Gender equality and expand the rights and opportunities of all women in our country in line with reforms aimed at ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men.

As a result of the comprehensive reforms carried out in recent years, a solid legal framework has been created in the Republic of Uzbekistan on issues of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men in all spheres of public life and activity, protecting women from harassment and violence.

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